

FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL CULTURE OF FUTURE DOCTORS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the issues of raising a solid foundation for the future medical culture and society, strengthening both material and spiritual attention to medical science.*

Keywords: *medical culture, the development of medical science, a solid foundation for the future, information technology.*

Introduction. Paying special attention to health care in our country, an industrial framework for providing medical services to the population, reforming the country's healthcare system and social protection of citizens have been created. In order to implement the important and effective tasks of "Development of the social sphere" defined in the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of the medical culture of the individual is considered a vital necessity. From the point of view of society, there is a need for intellectually, physically and psychologically healthy personnel with medical culture. The concept of medical culture of a person represents a system that relies on knowledge covering health, the ways and methods of its formation, strengthening and protection, and controls the behavior of people in the process of vital activity. In this regard, it is desirable to improve the determinants of psychological protection mechanisms that affect the development of a healthy student lifestyle, to deepen scientific research aimed at developing students' attitude to their health. Psychological characteristics of the development of medical culture in students Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-406 "On State Policy Regarding Youth" adopted on September 14, 2016, January 29, 2019 "Widely promoting a healthy lifestyle in Uzbekistan and involving the population in physical education and mass sports on" decisions, the concept of "Uzbekistan goals - 2030" and serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in other regulations and legal documents on the health of the country's population. Today, maintaining the health of the fourth generation is one of the most important current problems not only of the health organization, but also of educators and pedagogues. At the same time, it is known that any disease or deviation from a healthy lifestyle, even for a short time, changes the body's reactivity, impairs the functional state of the central nervous system, causes a decrease in work capacity, high fatigue and, as a result, a decrease in educational results. The current alarming situation requires the search for new, non-standard approaches to maintaining children's health during education and thus ensuring its success, as well as creating optimal conditions for promoting the basics of a healthy lifestyle. Although chronic illnesses or disabilities may occur at any age, the likelihood that a person will experience any activity limitation due to a chronic condition increases with age. In 2000, 35 million people — more than 12 percent of the total population — were 65 years or older. By 2050, it is expected that one in five Americans — 20 percent — will be elderly. The population will also become increasingly diverse. By 2050, racial and ethnic minorities will comprise 35 percent of the over 65 population. As the population at risk of chronic conditions becomes increasingly diverse, more attention to linguistic and cultural barriers to care will be necessary.

Having a regular doctor or a usual source of care facilitates the process of obtaining health care when it is needed. People who do not have a regular doctor or health care provider are less likely to obtain preventive services, or diagnosis, treatment, and management of chronic conditions. Health insurance coverage is also an important determinant of access to health care. Higher proportions of minorities compared to Whites do not have a usual source of care and do not have health insurance.

Research Methodology. Another psychological-pedagogical factor of development of medical culture among students is a healthy lifestyle. Lifestyle is a product of dialectical concepts in specific conditions, and it is a concept that includes life, work, rest, etc., expressed in a specific society, environment. Its components include not only socio-political and production activities, but also non-production activities, socio-cultural activities. Medical activism is also a type of it. In marriage, a person can fall into various impressions, adverse situations and circumstances. These, in turn, force people to have full knowledge about health, healthy lifestyle, education of population's attitude to their health and promotion of medical knowledge. A healthy lifestyle is a broad concept and consists of productive work, active recreation, physical education and sports, physical training, personal and psychohygiene, healthy eating, refraining from harmful habits, and annual medical check-ups. If every member of the society applies these in his life, he will live a healthy life. Movement and health. The main way to form a healthy lifestyle and prevent diseases is properly organized physical activity. As a result of the movement, the activity of various organs and systems of a person is regulated, and the disturbed activities are restored, and the activity for mental and physical work increases. For a person of any age, movement is an indicator of full life and activity. As a result of the movement, energy consumption increases, tissue supply with blood, oxygen and nutrients improves. The structure of heart muscle fibers is strengthened, the work of the hormonal and nervous system that controls the body is activated. Movement and physical exercises strengthen the bone system, increase muscle strength and maintain their uniform shape. Movement is very important for babies and school-aged children, it has a good effect on the formation of the child's body, the development of the musculoskeletal system, cardiovascular system, endocrine and other systems in the body.

Conclusion. At this point, if we focus on this problem, the disease is a violation of the normal life activity of the organism as a result of a functional or morphological disturbance of the organism.

The disease is divided into 4 periods:

1. latent (hidden) period
2. the appearance of symptoms of the disease.
3. the period of exacerbation of the disease
4. the end of the disease (recovery, relapse, from an acute form to a chronic form pass)

Acute diseases are registered annually. Chronic diseases are registered once a year. The disease is characterized as a disease of the entire population of a particular age, sex, professional and social group. Incidence rates are calculated per 1,000, per 10,000 or per 100,000 population. Diseases due to infectious, temporary loss of work ability are divided into occupational diseases.

The following diseases occur in Uzbekistan:

1. respiratory diseases
2. circulatory diseases
3. diseases of the nervous system and sensory organs

4. bone-muscle diseases
5. digestive diseases
6. mental illnesses.

From what has been discussed with above mentioned arguments it can be inferred that medical culture is at the root of these diseases. Therefore, development of medical culture of future doctors is a reason for prevention of diseases. Future doctors should take these factors into account and take measures in the healing process of their patients.

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